

DURABILITY AND RELIABILITY ASSESSMENT OF CARBON FIBER REINFORCED POLYMERS IN CIVIL APPLICATIONS

K.-Y. Kim^{1*}, J. H. Yoo², K. S. Lim², H. H. Jang²

¹Department of Textile Convergence of Biotechnology & Nanotechnology, Korea Institute of Industrial Technology, Ansan-si, South Korea,

²Technical Textile Center, Korea Institute of Industrial Technology, Ansan-si, South Korea,
*kkim@kitech.re.kr

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1 Introduction

Since carbon fibers were commercially available in 1970s, the development of carbon fiber reinforced polymers (CFRPs) has been driven mainly by high-performance and low-volume production industries like aerospace and sports due to high production costs resulting from expensive raw materials and labor intensive fabrication processes [1]. However, recently, the CFRPs have received much attention as industrial materials due to their advantages, such as high strength and stiffness to weight ratio, excellent corrosion resistance, and design flexibility. In particular, they are widely used in the construction and rehabilitation of civil engineering structures such as buildings and bridges. The CFRPs can reduce a burden on the weight of the structures and increase stiffness, strength and enduring durability of the structures [2-4].

The application of CFRPs for strengthening concrete structures provides efficient, lightweight, and noncorrosive properties and improves the load-bearing capacity and mechanical performance of the structures. These reinforcements are readily available in several forms, ranging from factory-made laminates to dry fiber sheets. The dry form can be wrapped to conform to the geometry of a structure before adding the polymer resin. The relatively thin profile of cured laminate systems is often desirable in the applications where aesthetics or access is a concern [5]. There is a tremendous need for a cost effective and durable method of repairing and strengthening concrete structures. This is apparent in deteriorating buildings, bridges and other structures due to the corrosion of steel reinforcements.

To strengthen the concrete structures with CFRPs are used externally bonded reinforcements (EBRs) that require the application of epoxy adhesive to bond between concrete and reinforcements. The EBRs are effective in increasing the flexural strength of concrete beams, but there are problems of premature failure such as peeling of CFRPs and failure of adherend. Therefore, recently, externally non-bonded reinforcements (ENBRs) have been developed for pre-stressed concrete structures in order to improve crack suppression, load-bearing capacity-rating and performance of construction structures by pre-stressing effects [6], as shown in Fig. 1.

Although the CFRP tendons are widely used for externally bonded reinforcements or externally non-bonded reinforcements, the limited information of their durability restricts their applications. The lifetime prediction of CFRPs is very important for a practical application in various industrial sectors, particularly, architecture and civil engineering due to a greater concern of safety and durability. In this study, the long-term durability evaluation and safety life-time prediction are performed through the assessment of long-term effects on the properties of the CFRP tendons through creep and accelerated hydrothermal aging tests.

2 Experimental

2.1 Carbon plate manufacture

Carbon fibers (CFA) were kindly provided by Hyosung Company, South Korea, and used for the manufacture of unidirectional flat strip CFRP tendons with the width of 50 mm and the thickness

of 1.2 mm by the pultrusion process. For comparison, the commercially available CFRP tendons (CFB) were purchased from SK Chemicals, which are currently used for pre-tensioning and post-tensioning tendons for building and bridge repair. The fiber volume fractions of these CFRP tendons were around 76 %.

2.2 Characterization

A dynamic mechanical analyzer (DMA, TA Instrument Q-series) was used to determine glass transition temperatures (T_g) of CFRPs at a heating rate of 2 °C/min and multiple frequencies of 0.3, 1, 10, 50, and 100 Hz in the 3-point bending mode. The tests were performed in both longitudinal and transverse directions along the fiber direction, and the average results were obtained.

Tensile and flexural tests were carried out in accordance to ASTM D3039 and ASTM D790, respectively. For the tensile and flexural tests, the pultruded composites were machined into the standard test specimens with a dimension of 200 mm × 13 mm (length × width) and 50 mm × 25 mm (length × width), respectively, using a diamond saw and a grinding machine. Aluminum end tabs were bonded to each end of the tensile specimens, leaving the test gage length of 150 mm. Tension tests were performed with an Instron 5567 at a cross head speed of 2 mm/min. Axial strains were measured using an extensometer with a gage length of 50 mm, and stresses were calculated dividing the applied load by the original cross-sectional area. Young's modulus and yield strength were determined from the slope of the initial straight line and the maximum stress of the stress-stress curves, respectively. For each specimen type, at least three specimens were tested only in the fiber direction. Three-point flexural tests were performed with the same machine as the tensile test with the test span length of 25 mm at a crosshead speed of 1 mm/min. The deflection at the mid-span of the specimen was determined from the crosshead displacement. According to ASTM D 790, the strength is defined by:

$$\sigma_{ult} = \frac{3PL}{2Bh^2} \quad (1)$$

and the elastic modulus is:

$$E_B = \frac{L^3 m}{4Bh^3} \quad (2)$$

where P is the maximum load, L is the testing span, B and h are the width and height respectively, and m the slope of the linear portion of the load-displacement curves. Four specimens were tested at each sample for longitudinal and transverse flexural tests to the fiber direction.

Tensile creep strength and rupture time were determined by JSCE-E 533, "Commentary on the Test Method for Creep Failure of Continuous Fiber Reinforcing Materials". A universal testing machine (MTS 810, USA) with hydraulic grips was used and operated at various creep stress levels of 100, 96, 92, 89, 86, 83, 80, 77, and 75 % of the average tensile strength of the CFRPs. The post-fracture surfaces of specimens were examined using scanning electron microscopy (SEM, Philips SEM505) with an accelerating voltage of 10 kV.

Hydrothermal aging tests were carried out according to "Standard Specification for Fiber Reinforced Polymer Composite Materials for Highway Bridge Applications, US Federal Highway Administration (FHWA) and ASTM" [7]. The test temperatures were determined by a reference temperature (T_{ref}), taken as 80 % of T_g , and ΔT is $([T_{ref} - 40^\circ\text{C}]/3)$. The four test temperatures are $T_1 = T_{ref}$, $T_2 = T_{ref} - \Delta T$, $T_2 = T_{ref} - 2\Delta T$, and $T_3 = T_{ref} - 3\Delta T$. The longitudinal samples with fiber direction along to the test span were immersed in de-ionized water at 40, 55, 70, 85 °C for the periods of 28, 56, 112 and 224 days.

3 Results and Discussion

3.1 Carbon fiber properties

CFA carbon fibers are on the developing stage, and commercially available carbon fibers (CFB) are used for comparison. Their tensile properties are given in Table 1 with the Weibull distribution shape parameter for the fiber strength as a function of gauge length. The Weibull distribution parameters are well defined elsewhere [8].

$$\ln\left[\ln\left(\frac{1}{1-F(x)}\right)\right] = \beta \ln x - \beta \ln \alpha \quad (3)$$

A high value of the shape parameter, β , indicates that flaws are evenly distributed throughout the material, whatever they are plentiful or not, and hence strength is nearly independent of the gauge length [9]. The low values indicate that flaws are fewer and less evenly distributed, causing greater scatter in fiber strength and the dependence on the gauge length. The CFA shows the lower strength and higher modulus with a wider range of the shape parameter (2.7 - 4.1), compared with those of the CFB fiber. The smaller shape parameter in the CFA fiber indicates a larger scatter of the strength and less evenly distributed flaws, leading to the stronger dependence on gauge length.

3.2 The tensile and flexural properties

The tensile modulus and strength of CFA and CFB tendons are summarized in Table 2 and 3, respectively. According to the American Concrete Institute (ACI) guideline, the design ultimate strength, f_{fu} , (DS) for CFRPs is suggested to ensure the effectiveness of the rehabilitation over the life of the structures, which can be expressed as,

$$\begin{aligned} f_{fu}^* &= \overline{f_{fu}} - 3\sigma \\ f_{fu} &= C_E f_{fu}^* \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

where $\overline{f_{fu}}$ is the mean strength and σ is the standard deviation of the test population. These statistically based ultimate tensile properties provide a 99.87 % probability that the indicated values are exceeded. For the exterior exposure with the environmental reduction factor C_E of 0.85, the design ultimate strength is 1955.6 MPa for the CFA tendon. If it is exposed to sustained and cyclic stresses such as creep or fatigue, the stress limit is the 0.55 times the design stress. The definition of the stress limit (SL) is based on the experimental result that the CFRPs can sustain 0.91 times their ultimate strength before encountering a creep-rupture with a safety factor of 1/0.60. The stress limit is 1075.6 MPa to avoid the creep-rupture of the CFRP tendon under sustained stresses or fatigue failure due to cyclic stresses for the CFA tendons. The CFB tendons have the design strength of 2897.8 MPa and the stress limit of

1593.8 MPa. The guideline is considered as the very stringent specification that the applicable stress is nearly 50 % level of the average strength.

Flexural test results were summarized in Table 4 and 5, tensile and flexural modulus has a similar value, but they have a remarkable difference in strength. It seems that the stress of the interface on fiber and matrix is different depending on the loading mode. The unidirectional composite specimens depend largely on the fiber properties. The unidirectional longitudinal specimen to fiber orientation depends mainly on the characteristics of reinforcing carbon fibers with high strength and high modulus whereas the properties of the transverse specimens can be found much lower because of matrix dominated properties of epoxy resin. The transverse tensile and flexural properties show insignificant difference between the CFA and CFB tendons.

3.2 Creep properties and reliability

Creep is the time dependent deformation under constant stress. Fig. 2 shows the experimental results of the creep rupture time at the various creep stresses of 100, 96, 92, 89, 86, 83, 80, 77, and 75 % of the tensile strength for the CFA and CFB tendons. The plots show the regression line for the correlation with stress and creep rupture time to predict creep-lifetime. According to the regression line, the creep strengths are predicted as 1774.0 MPa and 2325.1 MPa for 100 years (about 1,000,000 hours) service life for the CFA and CFB tendons, respectively. In addition, with a consideration of environmental degradation, the creep stress can be reduced to 1507.9 and 1976.3 MPa, respectively, which are the stresses multiplied by 0.85 of the environmental reduction factor for the exterior exposure condition as defined in ACI.

The experimental creep test results are used for reliability assessment and life time prediction with commercial software Minitab 14. The Weibull distribution is assumed for creep rupture time of three specimens at each stress level. Equation 5 is used to calculate B_{10} life, which is the time at which 10 % of a given product population will fail. η is Weibull scale parameter and β is the Weibull shape parameter.

$$t_{0.1}=B_{10}=\eta[-\ln(1-p)]^{\frac{1}{\beta}} \quad (5)$$

The regression curve between stress and B_{10} life in Fig. 3 can predict the stress level to ensure 100-year life span of the CFA and CFB plates at 1788 MPa and 2240 MPa, respectively, at the confidence level of 90 %. The creep reduction factors are 1.37 (100/73) and 1.55 (=100/64), respectively for the CFA and CFB tendons. The B_{10} life prediction is very similar to the test results shown in Fig. 2.

Because the fracture appearance and surfaces of the CFA and CFB are almost identical, only photographs and scanning electron microscope (SEM) micrographs for the CFA tendons are presented here, and the discussion of creep behavior is also applicable to the CFB tendons. Fig. 4 presented the photographs of the fracture appearance after the creep test. Fig. 4 (a) is the creep-fractured specimen at the creep stress level of 96 % of the tensile strength. Fig. 4 (b) ~ (f) are the photographs of the specimen of the lower stress levels of 92, 89, 86, 83, 75 %, respectively. The fracture mode in Fig.4 (a) shows the explosive type coded by XGM (eXplosive, Gage, Middle), specified in ASTM with excessive longitudinal splitting due to extensive matrix failure or fiber/matrix debonding. However, the fracture mode of Fig. 4 (b) ~ (f) is accompanied by a couple of longitudinal long splitting lines and delamination, such as the SGV (long-Splitting, Gage, Middle) failure mode. The different fracture mode can be attributed to energy absorption up to the break. The long splitting phenomenon can be seen in the lower stress levels where the crack initiates at the weakest interface between the fiber and matrix, and develops through the fiber/matrix interfacial debonding, leading to the final fracture. Therefore, in order to improve long-term creep resistance, the strong interfacial adhesion must be needed.

Fig. 5 shows the representative SEM micrographs of fracture surfaces of creep-fractured CFA tendons. For the high creep stress level, matrix fracture and few areas of fiber/matrix debonding are observed with some fiber fractures, implying that the breakdown of the composites was almost dominated by the failure of the matrix. On the other hand, the fracture surface at the lower creep stress shows that most fibers are freely separated from the matrix,

indication more extensive interfacial debonding. It is clear that the decrease in creep stress level changes the failure mode from cohesive matrix to adhesive interfacial failure. The interfacial dominated fracture surfaces may account for strong sensitivity of creep strength to the fiber/matrix interface with decreasing stress level.

3.3 Hydrothermal aging durability and reliability

Table 6 shows the change in the glass transition temperatures, T_g , measured for CFRP tendons by DMA tests. The T_g increases with increasing frequency, and the T_g of the longitudinal samples is higher than that in transverse direction due to reinforcing effects of carbon fibers for both CFA and CFB tendons. The lower T_g can accounts for stronger sensitivity of the matrix when the transverse samples are subject to the applied dynamic stress. The apparent activation energy for glass transition, ΔE_a , can be used to characterize the relationship between the shift of glass transition temperatures and test frequencies [10]. The activation energy represents the energy barrier of glass transition and can be calculated from the relationship between frequency and glass transition temperature through,

$$\Delta E_a = -R \left[\frac{d(\ln f)}{d(1/T_g)} \right] \quad (6)$$

where R is the Universal Gas Constant (8.31 Jmol⁻¹K⁻¹) and f is test frequency. The activation energy can be used as a means of monitoring material transition as a result of aging and/or environmental exposure [10]. As shown in Table 7, the longitudinal sample has much higher activation energy than that of the transverse sample, indicating that the latter is more susceptible to aging and can easily degrade under a certain environmental or service condition than the former. However, a significant difference cannot be observed between the CFA and CFB tendons due to the same epoxy matrix formulation.

Fig. 6 shows the effects of aging temperature and time on the tensile strength of the longitudinal CFA and CFB tendons. The strength is significantly reduced as the temperature and aging time increase for both specimens. The most significant reduction was found for the hydrothermally aged specimens at

the highest temperature of 85 °C. Such dependence can be explained by the removal of the matrix due to hydrolytic degradation and interfacial failure between matrix and fibers, which can be seen in the surface of the CFRP specimens, as illustrated in Fig. 7. Obviously, the reduction in the mechanical properties is due to the hydrolytic degradation in epoxy resins under humidity and elevated temperatures, leading to the weaker interface of the aged specimen because the failure mode changed from the matrix failure to more interface relevant failure with aging, as shown in Fig. 8.

The retention of the tensile strength for the hydrothermally aged samples is shown with aging time using a logarithmic scale in Fig. 9. As discussed before, the higher accelerated ageing can be seen at the highest temperature of 85 °C. The Arrhenius method is applied to predict the service life. The 80, 70, 60, 50 % data are plotted as a function of inverse temperatures in Fig. 8. The 80 % retention can be predicted at 17.46 °C (annual average maximum temperature in Seoul, Korea) over a hundred years through the extrapolated relationship, as shown in Fig. 9. The results can be explained by the pronounced effects of the hydrothermal aging on the matrix and/or interface rather than the carbon fibers. In the similar method to the creep strength, the reliability is evaluated with the Minitab software by assuming the Weibull distribution for the hydrothermal strength retention results. The regression curves between temperature and B_{10} life in Fig. 10 can predict 74 and 94 years for 80 % strength retention of the CFA and CFB plates, respectively, at the 90 % confidence level. However, it must be borne in mind that the accelerated tests are only valid in the same degradation mechanisms between the accelerated and actual service conditions.

3 Conclusions

In this study, the long-term durability evaluation and the safety life-time prediction were performed through the assessment of carbon fiber effects on the properties of the CFRP tendons with the use of creep rupture and accelerated hydrothermal aging tests. The creep strengths were predicted as 1774.0 MPa and 2325.1 MPa to ensure the 100 years (about 1,000,000 hours) service life for the CFA and CFB

tendons, respectively. However, in spite of the lower strength of CFA fibers, the lower value of the creep reduction factor for CFA tendons implied that the CFA fibers were more durable to the creep stress than the CFB fibers. From the hydrothermal aging tests, the CFA and CFB tendons showed the similar results that the 80 % retention can be predicted over a hundred years through the extrapolated relationship because the hydrothermal aging significantly affected on the matrix and/or interface rather than the carbon fibers. The reliability results show the similar B_{10} life to the predicted life time from the regression curves from experimental test results.

Table 1 Tensile properties of carbon fibers with Weibull distribution shape parameters

Carbon fibers	Gauge length [mm]	Modulus [GPa]	Mean strength [GPa]	Weibull shape parameter
CFA	10	260	4.1	2.7
	25	255	3.7	2.4
	50	267	3.4	4.1
CFB	10	233	5.2	3.5
	25	240	4.2	4.0
	50	219	3.5	4.0

Table 2 Tensile properties of CFA tendons

	Modulus [GPa]	Strength [MPa]	Strength -3σ [MPa]	DS [MPa]	SL [MPa]
1	174.5	2409.0	-	-	-
2	173.4	2397.7	-	-	-
3	179.3	2475.6	-	-	-
Mean	175.7	2427.3	2300.7	1955.6	1075.6
Std. Dev.	3.13	42.2	-	-	-

Table 3 Tensile properties of CFB tendons

	Modulus [GPa]	Strength [MPa]	Strength -3σ [MPa]	DS [MPa]	SL [MPa]
1	178.3	3534.0	-	-	-
2	174.3	3660.7	-	-	-
3	164.1	3633.8	-	-	-
Mean	172.2	3609.5	3409.2	2897.8	1593.8
Std. Dev.	7.32	66.8	-	-	-

Table 4 Flexural properties of CFA tendons

Specimen #	Longitudinal specimen		Transverse specimen	
	Modulus [GPa]	Strength [MPa]	Modulus [GPa]	Strength [MPa]
1	178.2	1586.8	13.5	105.9
2	165.9	1601.3	13.9	96.4
3	169.2	1605.2	12.7	99.6
Mean	171.1	1597.8	13.4	100.6
Std. Dev.	6.4	9.7	0.6	4.8

Table 5 Flexural properties of CFB tendons

Specimen #	Longitudinal specimen		Transverse specimen	
	Modulus [GPa]	Strength [MPa]	Modulus [GPa]	Strength [MPa]
1	178.3	2382.9	13.9	100.6
2	175.5	2444.9	13.0	92.1
3	175.5	2424.2	12.1	92.2
Mean	175.8	2417.2	13.0	95.0
Std. Dev.	1.93	31.6	0.9	4.9

Table 6 Glass transition temperatures of CFA and CFB tendons as a function of frequency using DMA

Specimen	Frequency [Hz]	T _g [°C]	
		CFA	CFB
Longitudinal	0.3	88	84
	1	90	89
	10	93	93
	50	97	95
	100	100	97
Transverse	0.3	56	58
	1	67	75
	10	77	66
	50	81	78
	100	78	70

Table 7 Activation energy of CFRP tendons

	Activation energy [kJ/mol]	
	CFA	CFB
Longitudinal	555.3	516.3
Transverse	217.9	167.5

Fig. 1. Externally non-bonded reinforcements for prestressed concrete structures.

Fig. 2. Creep rupture time at different stress level for CFA and CFB tendons.

Fig. 3. Regression curves between creep stress and B_{10} life; (a) CFA and (b) CFB tendons.

Fig. 3. Cont.

Fig. 4. Fracture appearances of creep-fractured CFA specimens.

Fig. 5. Creep fracture surfaces of CFA tendons.

Fig. 6. Tensile strength retention of CFRP tendons as a function of aging time; (a) CFA and (b) CFB tendons.

Fig. 7. SEM microscopes of surfaces of CFA tendons; (a) virgin and (b) hydrothermally aged specimens at 80 °C for 224 days.

Fig. 8. SEM microscopes of fracture surfaces of CFA tendons; (a) virgin and (b) hydrothermally aged specimens at 80 °C for 224 days.

Fig. 9. Tensile strength retention of CFRP tendons as a function of temperatures; (a) CFA and (b) CFB tendons.

Fig. 10. Cont

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Fig. 10. Regression curves of B_{10} life as a function of temperatures; (a) CFA and (b) CFB tendons.